

Misattribution of a Retrospective Case-Control Statistic as Prospective Epidemiologic Evidence in HFpEF: A Correction and a Caution for the Era of AI-Assisted Scientific Writing

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Submission history

This correspondence was submitted to the *European Journal of Heart Failure* on [19 May 2026] as a Letter to the Editor in response to the editorial by Störk and Tokcan (doi:10.1093/ejhf/xuag092). It was rejected by the editorial committee without substantive reviewer comment (rejection letter received [22 May 2026]; manuscript number EURJHF-26-726). It is posted here as a preprint to ensure the documented factual inaccuracy enters the public scientific record in a timely manner, consistent with the argument made in the correspondence itself.

ABSTRACT

A recent editorial published in the *European Journal of Heart Failure* stated that prospective studies report that up to 76% of patients with preserved left ventricular ejection fraction and unexplained breathlessness are ultimately diagnosed with HFpEF after invasive evaluation, citing Reddy et al. (*JAMA Cardiology*, 2022) as the supporting reference. This characterisation is factually incorrect in two respects: the cited study was a retrospective case-control study, not a prospective cohort study, and the 76% figure represents the case-control ratio of a deliberately constructed dataset of patients already referred for invasive haemodynamic exercise testing at tertiary centres, not the diagnostic yield of HFpEF in an unselected dyspnoeic population. Applying this figure to general ambulatory practice substantially overestimates HFpEF prevalence and misrepresents the diagnostic challenge in primary care. We document the inaccuracy, provide the correct interpretation of the cited study, and argue that timely correction is especially important in the current era of large language model-based AI writing assistants, which retrieve and reproduce published claims at scale without the contextual scrutiny a careful reader would apply. Uncorrected inaccuracies in authoritative publications risk propagating into the broader literature as established fact.

CORRESPONDENCE

A recent editorial by Störk and Tokcan, '*Navigating unexplained dyspnoea and the role of HFpEF diagnostic scores*,' published in the *European Journal of Heart Failure*,¹ contains a factual inaccuracy in its opening section that materially affects the clinical interpretation intended.

The authors state: '*prospective studies report that up to 76% of patients with preserved left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF \geq 50%) and unexplained breathlessness are ultimately diagnosed with HFpEF after invasive evaluation*,' citing Reddy et al. (*JAMA Cardiology*, 2022) as the supporting reference.² This characterisation is incorrect on two important counts.

First, the Reddy et al. study was a retrospective case-control study, not a prospective cohort study. Patients were specifically referred to six tertiary centres for invasive haemodynamic exercise testing because HFpEF was already clinically suspected — a highly pre-selected population with an elevated pre-test probability by design. The study explicitly follows the Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) reporting guideline for observational studies, and the authors acknowledge that referral patterns likely differed across institutions, limiting generalisability.

Second, the 76% figure (563 of 736 patients) represents the proportion of cases in a deliberately constructed case-control dataset in which cases were defined by elevated pulmonary capillary wedge pressure during exercise and controls were defined by normal rest and exercise haemodynamics with symptoms attributed to deconditioning. This figure is the case-control ratio of the study sample — not the diagnostic yield of HFpEF among unselected patients presenting with unexplained dyspnoea in clinical practice.

The correct interpretation of the 76% figure is that among patients sufficiently suspected of HFpEF to be referred for invasive haemodynamic exercise testing at academic tertiary centres, approximately three-quarters had haemodynamically confirmed HFpEF. This speaks to appropriate patient selection at specialist centres, not to the broader epidemiology of dyspnoea in ambulatory or primary care practice. Applying this figure to the general unexplained dyspnoea population substantially overestimates HFpEF prevalence and understates the diagnostic challenge at the primary and secondary care interface, where most patients with dyspnoea are first encountered and where the misclassification problem is most consequential.

This distinction matters clinically. It is precisely the heterogeneity of the dyspnoeic population, and the large proportion without true cardiac HFpEF, that makes accurate characterisation of diagnostic score performance so important in the context studied by Dhont and colleagues.³ The Störk editorial itself reviews the limitations of HFpEF scores, including their discordance and limited sensitivity — findings that are contextually undermined when the baseline prevalence of HFpEF in unselected dyspnoeic populations is overstated by a figure drawn from a pre-selected tertiary cohort.

Beyond the immediate clinical implications, there is a broader concern about the propagation of inaccurate statements in the medical literature that has assumed new

urgency in the current era. An erroneous figure cited in an authoritative editorial does not remain an isolated error; it enters the citation network and tends to be reproduced uncritically in subsequent reviews, guidelines, and educational materials, each repetition lending it additional apparent credibility. This process has accelerated substantially with the widespread adoption of large language model-based AI writing assistants, which synthesise information from published text at scale. When an inaccurate claim appears in a high-profile journal with an authoritative citation attached, it is liable to be retrieved and reproduced by AI systems without the contextual scrutiny that a careful reader would apply, propagating simultaneously across many manuscripts and acquiring the appearance of established fact through frequency and repetition alone.⁴ A misattribution that might once have persisted in a handful of secondary citations can now be embedded in the retrieved knowledge of AI systems consulted by future authors across disciplines and continents. The obligation to correct such errors promptly at the source has therefore never been greater. Timely correction in the original publication is the most effective means of preventing an inaccuracy from becoming an unchallenged assumption in the literature and, increasingly, in the training and retrieval patterns of AI systems that the next generation of clinician-scientists will routinely consult.

I respectfully document this inaccuracy for the public scientific record and note that the correct interpretation of the Reddy et al. data - that haemodynamically confirmed HFpEF was found in 76% of a carefully pre-selected tertiary referral cohort - remains an important and informative finding in its own right. It does not, however, support the claim that 76% of patients with unexplained dyspnoea and preserved LVEF in general clinical practice are ultimately diagnosed with HFpEF as the retrospective case-controlled studies can not determine the true incidence or prevalence of a disease.

DECLARATIONS

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